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**EXPLORING THE INTERPLAY OF GENERATIVE AI AND
ANTHROPOMORPHISM IN CONVERSATIONAL MARKETING:
CREATING MATRIX**

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Abstract: The study investigates the complex link between Generative Artificial Intelligence and Anthropomorphism in the context of Conversational Marketing. Through a comprehensive literature review, the study tracks the evolution of Conversational Marketing, highlighting the transformative role of Generative Artificial Intelligence and the significance of anthropomorphism in enhancing user experiences. Therefore, the current study's developed matrix reveals the impact of varied degrees of Generative Artificial Intelligence and Anthropomorphism on Conversational Marketing. Nevertheless, the synthesis of Generative Artificial Intelligence and Anthropomorphism offers vast potential in Conversational Marketing, but striking a balance between the two is crucial for optimal user experience and effective marketing strategies.

Keywords: conversational marketing, digital marketing, generative AI, anthropomorphism, user experience, artificial intelligence, chatbots.

In today's dynamic business environment, Conversational Marketing stands out as a transformative approach, reshaping the way businesses engage with their customers. Historically, marketing strategies were largely one-dimensional (Sinha & Singh, 2018), with businesses broadcasting their messages and customers passively receiving them. However, the rise of new technologies and changes in customer expectations caused a paradigm shift towards marketing methods that are more interactive and tailored to each person. Therefore, one of them is known as "conversational marketing," which places an emphasis, at its foundation, on real-time, meaningful dialogues between companies and their customers, with the goal of building deeper connections and more personalised experiences (Sotolongo & Copulsky, 2018; Israfilzade, 2021; 2023).

The primary purpose of this study is to investigate deep into the relationship of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism and interpret their combined impact on Conversational Marketing. Specifically, the research aims to understand the foundational principles and evolution of Conversational Marketing. Then to explore the transformative role and impact of Generative AI in shaping Conversational Marketing strategies. Finally, to introduce and explain a matrix that integrates varying degrees of both Generative AI and Anthropomorphism, providing insights into their implications on Conversational Marketing.

Conversational marketing leverages the potential of interactive dialogues to do more than just relay information — it deeply engages customers, facilitating a dynamic exchange where they transition from passive receivers to active participants. By tailoring conversations to each customer's individual context, interactions become more meaningful, personalized, and thus, more engaging (Zhang et al., 2018; Shumanov & Johnson, 2021). For instance, AI chatbots can handle multiple customer conversations simultaneously (Harbola, 2021), thus providing immediate responses and personalized experiences to a larger audience.

Conversational marketing is a unique and dynamic strategy that fundamentally revolves around *six key principles* (Table 1) that have been formulated specifically

for the purpose of this research (Israfilzade, 2021; 2023). First and foremost, it takes a customer-centric approach, focusing on addressing customer needs and interests to provide a tailored, personalized experience. It also underscores the value of real-time engagement, which involves promptly interacting with customers, significantly enhancing their satisfaction and overall experience. In addition, this marketing approach encourages interactive dialogues, fostering two-way communication and active customer participation rather than limiting them to passive receipt of marketing messages.

Table 1. Key principles of conversational marketing

PRINCIPLES OF CONVERSATIONAL MARKETING	DESCRIPTION
CUSTOMER-CENTRIC APPROACH	This strategy focuses on addressing the customer's needs and interests, aiming to provide a personalized experience.
REAL-TIME ENGAGEMENT	Conversational marketing emphasizes the importance of interacting with customers promptly, which enhances customer experience and satisfaction.
INTERACTIVE DIALOGUES	This approach encourages two-way communication and active customer involvement, shifting away from passive receipt of marketing messages.
DATA-DRIVEN INSIGHTS	Businesses can gain valuable insights into customer behaviour, preferences, and pain points by engaging in conversations with them.
OMNICHANNEL PRESENCE	Conversational marketing utilizes various platforms, such as social media, email, and chatbots, to interact with customers wherever they feel most comfortable.
BUILDING LONG-TERM RELATIONSHIPS	The approach is aimed not only at immediate sales but also at building long-term relationships with customers, fostering stronger connections and loyalty.

Source: created by author

Artificial Intelligence has significantly transformed the marketing landscape, and one of its critical subfields, Generative AI, is making substantial inroads in reshaping conversational marketing (Sotolongo & Copulsky, 2018; Kulkarni et al., 2019; Mayahi & Vidrih, 2022). Generative AI employs sophisticated machine

learning algorithms to generate novel and unique data from a given set of input data, paving the way for creative content generation possibilities (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Houde et al., 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2023).

Distinct from traditional AI, which mainly focuses on pattern recognition, decision-making, and data analysis, Generative AI embarks on a more creative route, exploring various content variations based on user input (Israfilzade, 2020). There are diverse models under Generative AI, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Transformer-based models like OpenAI's GPT. Each model has its strengths and specific applications. For example, GANs are popular for creating realistic imagery, while models like GPT have proven excellent in generating human-like text (Radford et al., 2019; Houde et al., 2020).

Anthropomorphism is the attribution of human-like characteristics, intentions, emotions, or behaviours to non-human entities or objects (Epley, Waytz, & Cacioppo, 2007). The concept is foundational in human cognition and is often automatic and unconscious (Guthrie, 1993). In the realm of artificial intelligence, and particularly in conversational marketing, anthropomorphism is utilized to design and implement conversational agents that mimic human-like qualities, fostering a sense of familiarity and improving the overall user experience.

The advent of Anthropomorphic Generative AI has unlocked revolutionary possibilities in conversational marketing. More than mere communication facilitators, anthropomorphic conversational agents are playing increasingly sophisticated roles in shaping the dynamics of customer-business interactions. Anthropomorphic Generative AI excels in crafting and maintaining human-like interactions in the context of conversational marketing. This unique feature offers significant advantages to marketers, helping them deepen customer relationships and carve a competitive edge in the marketplace (Van Doorn et al., 2017).

Striking a balance in the application of anthropomorphism within conversational marketing is crucial. It necessitates a well-thought-out approach that transcends merely imbuing AI systems with human-like attributes. The design and competencies of conversational agents should align with user expectations to prevent

any discordance or deception that might result from overstating the AI's capabilities. A properly anthropomorphized AI can contribute to enhanced interaction quality, increased user satisfaction, and a more effective marketing strategy (Jakesch et al., 2019).

Ultimately, the challenge lies in finding the sweet spot between incorporating appealing human-like traits and managing user expectations regarding the AI's abilities. Excessive anthropomorphism can result in unrealistic expectations, while too little can render the AI impersonal and mechanical. Thus, navigating this delicate balance is key to leveraging the full potential of Anthropomorphic Generative AI in conversational marketing.

This study dives deep into the nexus of Generative AI and anthropomorphism, elucidating their combined influence on conversational marketing. By creating a matrix that integrates varying degrees of both factors, we seek to chart out the potential realms of engagement and disengagement. This analytical framework, dubbed *"Implications of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism Levels on Conversational Marketing,"* aims to guide marketers, designers, and business strategists on how to best utilize AI technologies in interactive marketing contexts (Table 2). The matrix not only highlights the qualitative differences in interactions across different AI-anthropomorphism combinations but also underscores the potential pitfalls and opportunities inherent in each. As we traverse the matrix, readers will gain insights into how different combinations impact user satisfaction, trust, and the overall efficacy of conversational marketing strategies.

Table 2
Implications of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism Levels on Conversational Marketing

	Low Anthropomorphism	High Anthropomorphism
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<p>Low Generative AI</p>	<p>Conversational Marketing Impact: Limited engagement due to lack of personalization and human-like interaction. Effective for simple, transactional interactions.</p>	<p>Conversational Marketing Impact: Increased engagement due to a relatable, human-like interface. Risk of disappointment if AI fails to deliver human-like responses.</p>
<p>High Generative AI</p>	<p>Conversational Marketing Impact: Improved engagement due to personalized responses. Potential disengagement if responses seem inauthentic or machine-like.</p>	<p>Conversational Marketing Impact: Highly engaging and dynamic conversations are possible. Risk of discomfort or dissonance if AI appears too human-like or fails to meet high expectations.</p>

Source: created by author

This table, titled "Implications of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism Levels on Conversational Marketing", presents a matrix that categorizes the potential impact of varying degrees of anthropomorphism and Generative AI sophistication on conversational marketing. The table is divided into four quadrants, each representing a unique combination of anthropomorphism and AI sophistication.

The union of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism plays a pivotal role in shaping these digital dialogues. While Generative AI offers the potential for dynamic, personalized interactions, Anthropomorphism can enhance the relatability and appeal of these digital entities. Yet, the blend of these elements doesn't always result in optimal engagement. Figure 1 below, titled 'The Conversational Marketing Matrix: Intersections of AI and Anthropomorphism', offers a visual representation, categorizing various combinations of these factors into four distinct quadrants. Each quadrant encapsulates a specific interaction style, highlighting the synergies and potential pitfalls associated with varying levels of AI sophistication and anthropomorphic design.

Figure 1. The Conversational Marketing Matrix: Intersections of AI and Anthropomorphism

Source: created by author

It's divided into four distinct quadrants, each representing a unique combination of these two variables:

1. **Digital Clerk (Low Generative AI & Low Anthropomorphism):** Stripped of any pretence, these are the simple, straightforward digital interfaces that users often interact with for transactional or basic informational needs. Their interactions are direct and to the point, without any added layer of personalization or human touch.
2. **Humanoid Echo (Low Generative AI & High Anthropomorphism):** This quadrant represents chatbots or AI tools that are dressed up with a human-like facade, echoing back pre-set responses. While they may seem human-like at first glance, their interactions are limited to predefined patterns. Users may initially be drawn in by the familiar, relatable appearance but might eventually feel disappointed by the lack of adaptive conversation.
3. **Silent Genius (High Generative AI & Low Anthropomorphism):** These are the behind-the-scenes powerhouses. Devoid of a human-like appearance, they compensate with their sheer intelligence. They can provide highly personalized and relevant responses, but their lack of human-likeness can sometimes make them feel distant or overly mechanical to some users.

4. **Almost Human (High Generative AI & High Anthropomorphism):**

Representing the pinnacle of technological sophistication in the realm of conversational AI, these entities possess both a human-like appearance and an advanced capacity for dynamic interaction. They can learn, adapt, and converse in intricate ways. However, a careful balance is needed to prevent an uncanny valley effect. The design and communication strategy must ensure that the human-like presentation does not create unrealistic expectations of human-level understanding and responses.

In navigating the landscape of conversational marketing, businesses must identify where their strategies fit within these quadrants. By doing so, they can better tailor their approaches, optimizing for user engagement, satisfaction, and overall effectiveness.

While theoretical matrices and categorizations provide a structured framework to understand the dynamics of Anthropomorphism and Generative AI, practical examples ground these concepts in tangible scenarios, offering a lucid view of their implications in real-world interactions. Such examples not only illuminate the diverse outcomes stemming from different combinations of anthropomorphism and AI sophistication but also offer critical insights for businesses aiming to harness the power of conversational marketing. By examining and reflecting on these practical instances, designers, marketers, and AI developers can better navigate the complexities of user expectations and technological capabilities. Ultimately, it's through this melding of theory and practice that one can truly grasp the nuances and potential of AI-driven conversational interfaces.

Therefore, here are practical examples for each quadrant:

1. **Low Anthropomorphism and Low Generative AI** – Basic chatbots used in customer service represent this category. For example, a chatbot that responds to specific keywords with pre-programmed responses. These bots can provide quick answers to simple queries like "What are your operating hours?", but they lack the ability to understand complex requests or engage in natural, dynamic conversations.

2. **Low Anthropomorphism and High Generative AI** – A good example here would be Google's search engine. While it's not anthropomorphic and doesn't exhibit human-like traits, its advanced generative capabilities allow it to provide highly personalized and contextually relevant search results. However, its interaction lacks the 'personal touch' that comes with more human-like interactions.
3. **High Anthropomorphism and Low Generative AI** – Some early versions of virtual assistants like Apple's Siri or Amazon's Alexa might fall into this category. They were given human-like voices and personalities to enhance user engagement, but initially, they had limited generative capabilities and could only respond to a relatively narrow set of commands. This could lead to situations where the user expectation (based on the human-like presentation) exceeded the AI's actual capabilities, resulting in potential dissonance.
4. **High Anthropomorphism and High Generative AI** – An advanced version of a virtual assistant like Alexa, which has evolved significantly since its introduction, could fit in this quadrant. It exhibits both high human-like characteristics (voice, responsiveness) and advanced generative capabilities (understanding and responding to a wide array of commands, learning from user interaction). However, even with these advancements, the design needs to prevent an uncanny valley effect where the AI's human-like characteristics create an expectation of perfect human-like understanding and responses, which no AI can fully deliver as of now. This challenge emphasizes the need for transparent communication about the AI's capabilities and limitations.

These examples highlight the varied implications of anthropomorphic design and generative AI capabilities on the effectiveness and user perception of AI systems in conversational marketing. Each combination presents its own set of opportunities and challenges that must be carefully considered in the design and implementation process.

The study into the combination of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism in Conversational Marketing has shown a new way for customers and businesses to talk

to each other. The study shows that conversational marketing is not just about real-time conversations, but also about making real, personal relationships. When Generative AI is added to this paradigm, it makes it more powerful, allowing for dynamic, context-sensitive interactions that are as deep and organic as human conversations.

In conclusion, the combination of Generative AI and Anthropomorphism in Conversational Marketing introduces a new era of more meaningful interactions with customers. As technology continues to evolve and consumer expectations shift, it is imperative for businesses to stay agile, harnessing the insights from this research to craft marketing strategies that are not only effective but also deeply resonant. The journey of Conversational Marketing is just beginning, and its potential is boundless.

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